

Utilization of Paper and Fruit Peel Waste for Biofertilizer Production

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Abstract:

In this study, we converted institutional paper waste and fruit peels into biofertilizers to enhance the growth and yield of economically important agricultural crops. Pre-treated paper waste was subjected to vermicomposting using farmyard manure, and *Eisenia fetida* worms and rigorously analysing the results for macro and micronutrients, earthworm mortality rates, and heavy metal presence. Additionally, fruit peels from oranges and sweet limes were quantified and used in plant growth experiments. Soil macro and micronutrient levels were measured before and after application. The study identified an optimal compost setup: 2 kg paper waste, 1 kg cow dung, and 1 kg cardboard waste, yielding 3.1 kg of vermicompost per 12 kg initial waste, enriched with N (0.71%), P (0.27%), and K (1.26%) per hectare, free from heavy metals. Fruit peel biofertilizers significantly boosted soil nutrient levels of Mustard using sweet lime peel at 5g/100 ml formulation and Orange at 1g/100 ml formulation, Wheat using orange peel at 1g/100 ml formulation and sweet lime for 5g/100 ml formulation, Fenugreek using orange peel at 4g/100 ml formulation and sweet lime peel at 5g/100 ml formulation in treated soils. The study highlighted 5g/100 ml as an effective concentration for increasing nutrient content across all three plant types, underscoring the potential of these biofertilizers to contribute essential nutrients for sustainable agriculture.

Keywords: Biofertilizers, Institutional paper waste, Fruit peels, Vermicomposting, Nutrient analysis, Agricultural sustainability.

I. INTRODUCTION

The present study introduces a novel concept for in-house solid waste management. In the era of nature preservation and soil conservation, adopting more righteous approaches such as educational institute waste management by stakeholders can bring about a revolutionary change in society. Considering other available waste management techniques, sustainable waste management is no longer an option; it is the only solution. Landfilling depletes land availability, emits harmful gases, and affects mental health near landfill sites. Incineration, while easy, produces maximum harmful gas emissions. Discarding waste into water bodies disrupts marine life and water purity. Recycling, although efficient, requires machinery, manpower, and resources, making it unsustainable. The management of solid waste poses a significant challenge for heavily populated developing countries that generate substantial quantities of waste. The three essential components for establishing a sustainable solid waste management system are proper awareness, meticulous planning, and effective implementation [1-3].

Paper waste is a common by-product of various human activities, including offices, schools, and households. Disposing of paper waste in landfills contributes to environmental pollution and resource depletion. However, there is a sustainable and eco-friendly solution: vermicomposting. Vermicomposting is a natural process that utilizes earthworms to decompose organic materials, including paper waste. In this process, earthworms consume paper waste and transform it into nutrient-rich vermicompost (also known as worm castings). Vermicompost is a valuable organic fertilizer that enhances soil fertility, promotes plant growth, and reduces the need for chemical fertilizers [4]. The decomposition of paper waste through vermicomposting not only diverts waste from landfills but also contributes to soil health and sustainable agriculture. By exploiting the inherent characteristics of paper waste and its popular breakdown by bacteria into compost, the process of composting transforms waste into a useful resource, thus supporting environmental sustainability and (re)favours beneficial soil microflora [5]. By harnessing the power of earthworms, we can turn paper waste into a valuable resource while minimizing environmental impact. In this study, we explore the effectiveness of vermicomposting as a method for paper waste management and discuss its benefits for both waste reduction and soil enrichment [6]. Composting is a natural oxygen-based process that plays an important role in comprehensive waste management and farming enterprises. It involves decomposition of organic material by microorganisms; in this environment oxygen is present 'compost' or humus being produced as one result. In this process of composting, microorganisms use up oxygen as they break down organic matter, meanwhile emitting heat, water vapor and gases like carbon dioxide (CO₂) in the residue. As a result of this microbial activity the bulky organic materials are gradually transformed downwards [7].

Fruit peels, often discarded as waste, contain valuable nutrients and organic compounds that can be harnessed for sustainable agricultural practices. As the world faces challenges related to soil degradation, chemical fertilizers, and environmental

pollution, the need for eco-friendly alternatives becomes crucial. Biofertilizers derived from fruit peels offer a promising solution as fruit peels are rich in essential nutrients such as potassium, phosphorus, calcium, and micronutrients. These nutrients are vital for plant growth, flowering, and fruit development [8]. Fruit peels contribute organic matter to the soil, improving its structure, water retention, and microbial activity. Unlike synthetic fertilizers, biofertilizers enhance soil health without harmful chemical residues. Utilizing fruit peels as biofertilizers reduces waste and minimizes the environmental impact. Farmers can produce biofertilizers locally, reducing dependence on expensive chemical fertilizers. Fruit peel biofertilizers can be applied directly to the soil or as foliar sprays. Their slow-release nature ensures sustained nutrient availability to plants. Biofertilizers derived from fruit peels offer a cost-effective alternative to synthetic fertilizers, thereby reducing production costs for farmers while maintaining soil fertility. The utilization of orange (*Citrus sinensis*) and sweet lime (*Citrus limetta*) peels as biofertilizers presents a win-win solution for addressing fruit peel waste management challenges while promoting sustainable agriculture and soil health enhancement. By harnessing the nutritional richness of these often-overlooked resources, we can create a more environmentally friendly and economically viable approach to fertilization in agriculture [9, 10].

In this study, we investigated the science behind fruit peel biofertilizers, explore their effectiveness, and discuss their potential role in sustainable agriculture. By converting fruit waste into a valuable resource, we contribute to both soil fertility and environmental conservation.

II. MATERIALS AND METHOD

A. Collection and sorting of solid waste

Paper waste decomposition using vermicomposting was conducted at the C. G. Bhakta Institute of Biotechnology, an integral part of Uka Tarsadia University, serving as the pilot-scale study site with the aim of establishing a comprehensive and sustainable waste management system applicable to other university departments. Solid waste was systematically collected from various locations within the institute on a daily basis and sorted into organic and non-organic categories, with organic waste earmarked for vermicomposting. Three distinct sites within the institute were selected for sample collection to represent the entire department's solid waste. The amount of waste generated was meticulously recorded and tracked, while visual inspection and manual sorting were employed to categorize waste into compostable and non-compostable materials. Organic solid waste underwent vermicomposting, facilitated by earthworms, in a specifically created compost vessel. Two experimental setups were prepared, each consisting of a control and five compost setups with varying compositions of cow dung, paper waste, and cardboard waste, aimed at studying the decomposition process [11-13]. The vermicomposting setup involved organic solid waste undergoing natural decomposition facilitated by earthworms, with dedicated compost vessels created for this purpose. Two experimental setups were established for the study. There are approximately 8000 known earthworm species, but only 7 species are suitable for vermicomposting. These species belong to the epigeic category, such as *Eisenia foetida*, *Perionyx excavatus*, and *Eudrilus eugeniae*. *Eisenia foetida* is particularly renowned worldwide for vermicomposting due to its temperature tolerance (10-35 °C), resistance to diseases, rapid reproduction, high cocoon production rate, short life cycle, and efficient organic matter consumption which was employed in present study. In the first setup, labelled as 1.1 to 1.5, along with a control, five compost setups were arranged with a ratio of 1 kg cow dung to 2 kg paper waste per setup, totalling 9 kg of waste per setup. The second setup, labelled as 2.1 to 2.5, also included a control and five compost setups, with a composition of 1 kg cow dung, 2 kg paper waste, and 1 kg cardboard waste per setup, amounting to 12 kg of waste per setup. Each setup was replicated three times to ensure the reliability of the experimental results. Also, for both the vermicompost setups the nitrogen ratio was balanced by adding dried leaves as base and cover of the vermicompost vessel.

First Setup: In this study, the chosen method was Vessel Vermicomposting, a process involving the composting of organic materials within enclosed containers. This method utilizes aeration and mechanical turning of the organic matter at regular intervals to facilitate decomposition. Vessel composting involves processing compost in closed containers, with mechanical turning of organic matter at regular intervals [14]. Additionally, Vermicomposting incorporates the introduction of earthworms, specifically *Eisenia foetida*, to aid in the breakdown of organic matter. These earthworms consume the organic material, producing nutrient-rich castings that enhance soil fertility and promote plant growth. The aerobic composting process began with a soil bedding layer, followed by the addition of 25 clitellate earthworms. The subsequent layer consisted of dried cow dung bedding, which served as a source of nutrition for the earthworms during their initial multiplication phase. A layer of paper waste, pre-treated for 15 days to enhance decomposition (by soaking shredded paper waste in a waste container), was added to provide further organic matter for the earthworms.

Second Setup: The aerobic composting procedure commenced with the establishment of a basal layer comprising soil bedding, onto which 25 clitellate earthworms were introduced. Subsequently, a stratum of desiccated cow dung bedding was administered to sustain the earthworm population during their initial reproductive phase. Following this, a layer of paper waste, pre-conditioned for 15 days to expedite decomposition (via immersion of shredded paper waste in a waste receptacle), was

incorporated to augment the organic substrate accessible to the earthworms. Sequentially, an additional stratum of pre-conditioned cardboard, subjected to identical decomposition-enhancing treatment, was integrated into the composting setup.

Vermicomposting Process: The composting process unfolds in three distinct phases mesophilic phase, thermophilic phase and maturation phase, each characterized by specific temperature changes and microbial activity [15].

Both setups underwent regular monitoring for worm proliferation, moisture levels, and pH, with three replications each maintained for a duration of 50 days (Subsequent cycles were maintained). Subsequently, the worm castings or vermicompost were harvested, followed by sieving, drying, and nutritional content analysis.

During and post vermicomposting, data collection and analysis encompassed various aspects. Mortality rate analysis involved the regular observation and recording of earthworm mortality in each setup, including categorization into cocoons, immature, and mature worms during analysis. Nutrient analysis, focusing on Nitrogen, Phosphorus, and Potassium (NPK), was conducted using methods such as the Modified Kjeldahl Method for Nitrogen, Flame Photometer method for Potassium, and Bray P2 Method for Phosphorus. Micronutrient analysis evaluated essential micronutrients like iron, zinc, and copper, utilizing Atomic Absorption Spectroscopy. Furthermore, heavy metal analysis assessed the concentration of heavy metals such as lead and cadmium, employing ICP Spectroscopy (Inductively Coupled Plasma). These comprehensive analyses provided insights into the transformation of waste into nutrient-rich vermicompost and its potential agricultural applications.[16].

Fig.1 The process and steps involved in utilizing paper waste for vermicomposting.

As indicated in **fig.1**, unsegregated waste collected from dustbins underwent a process of segregation by hand sorting, followed by characterization and quantification using a digital spring balance. Papers from the waste were manually shredded and then pre-treated with water for 15 days to facilitate composting. Two vessel vermicompost setups, labelled 1 and 2, were created, each with five replicates. These setups included layers of paper, cow dung, 25 mature earthworms, and soil bedding. Setup 2 differed by having additional layers of cardboard. After 50 days, the compost was harvested, sieved, and dried for subsequent analysis. Various tests were conducted, including examination of NPK levels, heavy metals, and micronutrients. Additionally, pot assays were performed using fenugreek, wheat, and mustard plants.

B. Collection and preparation of fruit peels

The process of collecting and preparing fruit peels for experimentation involved meticulous steps to ensure consistency and efficacy. Initially, sweet lime and orange peels were sourced from the university juice centre, emphasizing freshness and quality. Upon collection, the peels underwent a thorough washing procedure to eliminate any contaminants that might interfere with subsequent analyses. Subsequently, the cleaned peels were subjected to air-drying to diminish moisture content, a crucial step to prevent spoilage and ensure stability during storage. Once dried, the peels were finely ground into a powder form, employing precision to achieve a consistent texture. This powder underwent sieving to attain uniform particle size, optimizing its integration into subsequent formulations. Formulation of liquid extracts ensued; wherein varying amounts of fruit peel powder were combined with 100 ml of distilled water to create different concentrations. Rigorous mixing was applied to ensure

homogeneity across all formulations. The preparation of plantation pots involved pre-treating soil with the fruit peel formulations, with each pot receiving a specific concentration based on the amount of peel powder. Control pots, serving as comparative references, were treated solely with distilled water, devoid of peel powder. Following soil preparation, seeding and planting commenced, with fenugreek, mustard, and wheat seeds evenly distributed across the treated soil in each pot. The experimental setup comprised distinct treatments, including control pots without peel powder and pots with varying concentrations of peel powder, with multiple replicates established for each treatment to enable robust statistical analysis and reliable conclusions [17].

The utilization process of citrus fruit peels, beginning with collection, washing, drying, grinding, and sieving is illustrated in **fig. 2**. Various formulations were prepared by mixing 1, 2, 3, 4 and 5 grams of orange and sweet lime powder with 100ml of distilled water. These formulations were then applied to the soil, and the soil samples were subsequently tested for macronutrient content and growth analysis.

In the soil and plant assessment phase, soil samples were systematically obtained from each pot following a designated growth period, enabling a comprehensive understanding of soil health. NPK analysis was conducted on these soil samples to evaluate their nutrient content, providing crucial insights into soil fertility and potential deficiencies. Concurrently, data collection involved recording plant growth parameters such as height and biomass, providing valuable indicators of plant vigor and productivity. Furthermore, the study assessed nutrient uptake by the plants, elucidating their capacity to absorb essential elements from the soil. The findings illuminated the diverse effects of fruit peel application across different plant species, showcasing varied responses observed in plant growth and nutrient utilization. This variability underscores the intricacies of plant-soil interactions, emphasizing the need for tailored organic waste recycling strategies to meet specific crop requirements, as discussed in the study's results.

Fig. 2 The process and steps involved in utilizing fruit peel waste as biofertilizer.

III. RESULTS

Solid waste quantification at the C. G. Bhakta Institute of Biotechnology was conducted daily using a hanging weigh balance. The institute's routine activities generate a significant amount of solid waste, with the rate of generation largely dependent on the population within the department. Seasonal variations significantly influence the waste generation rate. During the first study period (P1), the institute produced an average of 47.32 kg/day of solid waste, which decreased to 33.09 kg/day in the second study period (P2). The waste generation rates at the selected sampling sites were as follows: 25.2 kg/day (53.25%) from SCS-1, 14.5 kg/day (30.64%) from SCS-2, and 7.62 kg/day (16.10%) from SCS-3 during P1. These rates changed to 16.97 kg/day (51.28%) from SCS-1, 10.2 kg/day (30.82%) from SCS-2, and 5.92 kg/day (17.89%) from SCS-3 during P2. On a monthly basis, the institute generated an average total of 1198 kg during P1 and 840 kg during P2. The monthly waste generation rates at the selected sampling sites were as follows: 614.99 kg/month (51.33%) from SCS-1, 364.1 kg/month (30.39%) from SCS-2, and 219.37 kg/month (18.31%) from SCS-3 during P1. These rates changed to 416.94 kg/month (49.63%) from SCS-1, 259.06 kg/month (30.84%) from SCS-2, and 164 kg/month (19.52%) from SCS-3 during P2.

The waste generated at the C.G. Bhakta Institute of Biotechnology is predominantly composed of paper and cardboard materials (e.g., newspapers, rough papers, white papers, cartons, magazines), accounting for 414 kgs/month or 66% of the total waste. Plastic waste (e.g., plastic bags, plastic bottles, plastic packages) constitutes about 143 kgs/month or 24% of the total waste. Glass waste (e.g., bottles, broken glasses, glass containers) contributes approximately 21.42 kgs/month or 4%, while other types of waste make up about 36.57 kg/month or 6% of the total waste generated.

The study reveals that, on average, about 65% of the total waste generated at the C.G. Bhakta Institute of Biotechnology is potentially compostable.

As explained in **Table 1**, the comparative data between setup 1 and setup 2, distinguished by their utilization of varying quantities of waste 9 kg for setup 1 and 12 kg for setup 2 several significant observations were obtained. The setup 1 displayed elevated nitrogen levels in its compost particularly in setup 1.4, whereas setup 2 exhibited peak nitrogen content in setup 2.2. For phosphorus enrichment, setup 1.4 excelled for setup 1, while setup 2.2 demonstrated the highest levels for setup 2. In terms of potassium, setup 1.2 and setup 2.1 showed maximum concentration for their respective setups. Also, neither setup 1 nor setup 2 recorded any mortality rates, ensuring the conducive environment for worm activity in both settings. Furthermore, both setups demonstrated significant enrichment of macro and micronutrients in the compost compared to the control, underscoring the effectiveness of vermicomposting in augmenting compost nutrient compositions. These variations in nutrient enrichment indicate the complex relationship between waste composition and quantity, highlighting the need for tailored waste management methods. The absence of observed mortality rates underscores the viability of both setups for sustainable waste management and nutrient recycling applications.

Table 1: Comparative Analysis of Treatment, Control, Mortality Rate of Worms, and Macro & Micronutrient Content in Both Setups

In each setup, a total of 9 kg waste was utilized, and 25 mature clitellate worms were employed

Setup 1	MWO Nos.	IMO Nos.	CO Nos.	TV kg	N (kg/ha)	P (kg/ha)	K (kg/ha)	Fe ppm	Zn ppm	Cu ppm	Mn ppm	Na Ppm
C	12	74	98	1.90	0.20	0.12	0.65	4.84	0.30	0.45	4.66	18.12
CS 1.1	20	113	178	1.78	0.82	0.20	0.99	16.67	1.30	4.23	12.07	21.38
CS 1.2	28	185	92	2.10	0.96	0.27	1.20	10.23	1.21	3.54	9.34	19.21
CS 1.3	54	107	183	1.80	0.61	0.12	0.85	15.10	1.29	3.73	10.56	21.23
CS 1.4	25	79	162	2.20	0.52	0.38	0.98	16.44	1.44	5.81	11.21	22.65
CS 1.5	34	146	127	1.89	0.65	0.16	1.09	15.87	1.30	4.76	10.11	19.31

In each setup, a total of 12 kg waste was utilized, and 25 mature clitellate worms were employed

Setup 2	MWO Nos.	IMO Nos.	CO Nos.	TV kg	N (kg/ha)	P (kg/ha)	K (kg/ha)	Fe ppm	Zn ppm	Cu ppm	Mn Ppm	Na Ppm
C	8	64	56	2.80	0.87	0.31	0.87	6.37	0.50	0.81	6.78	20.13
CS 2.1	67	55	197	3.10	0.71	0.27	1.26	19.34	1.54	6.81	16.43	23.56
CS 2.2	24	53	177	2.92	0.94	0.32	1.10	23.87	2.11	6.87	18.12	24.78
CS 2.3	25	85	192	2.71	0.84	0.15	0.98	19.45	1.61	7.32	16.78	24.20
CS 2.4	20	83	183	3.20	0.59	0.24	1.12	20.56	1.22	7.44	17.66	22.14
CS 2.5	34	59	172	2.90	0.62	0.17	1.20	25.87	1.80	6.34	17.54	22.67

Key: C: Control, CS: Compost Setup (each with 3 replicates), **MWO:** Mature Worms Obtained, **IMO:** Immature Worms Obtained, **CO:** Cocoons Obtained, **TV:** Total Vermicompost (in kg), **N:** Nitrogen, **P:** Phosphorous, **K:** Potassium, **Fe:** Ferrous, **Zn:** Zinc, **Cu:** Copper, **Mn:** Manganese, **Na:** Sodium.

As indicated in **Table 2**, our compost displayed negligible levels of heavy metals. This proves its suitability for field trials, affirming its safety and efficacy for agricultural applications.

As shown in **Table 3**, comparison of orange and sweet lime peels effects on fenugreek plant growth and soil nutrient content provides interesting findings. Both types of fruit peels showed variations in plant responses, especially in stem girth and leaf size. Soil nutrient levels, including nitrogen (N), phosphorus (P), and potassium (K), increased with higher concentrations of fruit peel extract. This suggests a connection between the potency of peel extract in enhancing plant growth and its nutrient content. When compared with control both the fruit peel extracts showed an increase in soil nutrients.

Fig. 3 clearly shows the difference in growth, stem girth, and leaf size between the treated (T) and control (C) fenugreek plants. The test results clearly indicate a significant improvement in the health of fenugreek plants treated with citrus fruit peel formulations compared to the control group, which did not receive any fruit peel formulations. Particularly noteworthy is the

robust growth observed in terms of stem girth and leaf size in the treated fenugreek plants. This suggests that the application of orange and sweet lime peel formulations has a positive impact on fenugreek plant health and growth. The enhanced stem girth and larger leaf size indicate improved plant vigor and vitality, likely due to the nutrients and bioactive compounds present in the fruit peel formulations.

Table 4 presents a comparative analysis of the effects of orange and sweet lime peels on wheat plant growth and soil nutrient content. Both types of fruit peels exhibit variations in plant responses, particularly in terms of comparative leaf size. Notably, as the concentration of fruit peel extract increases, there is a corresponding increase in the levels of nitrogen (N), phosphorus (P), and potassium (K) in the soil. This suggests a positive correlation between the concentration of fruit peel extract and soil nutrient content. Additionally, orange peel extract consistently shows more pronounced effects on wheat plant growth, with improved leaf size compared to sweet lime peel extract.

Table 2: Heavy Metal Analysis of Vermicompost Manure Using ICP Spectroscopy (Inductively Coupled Plasma) - Sample CS 2.1 (sample of compost setup 2.1 was selected since it exhibited a satisfactory quantity of both macro and micronutrients and was chosen as a representative sample)

Heavy Metal	Amount (ppm)	Heavy Metal Content
Cadmium (Cd)	Not detected	5.00
Chromium (Cr)	19.68	50.00
Nickel (Ni)	11.47	50.00
Lead (Pb)	3.42	100.00

Table 3: Comparative Analysis of Orange and Sweet Lime Peels on Fenugreek Plant Growth and Soil Nutrient Content

Fruit peel	Plant	FC (gm/100ml D/W)	Stem Girth	Comparative Leaf Size	N (kg/ha)	P (kg/ha)	K (kg/ha)
Orange (<i>Citrus sinenses</i>)	Fenugreek (<i>Trigonella foenum- graecum</i>)	Control	Moderate	Shrivel	182.10	27	231
		1	Moderate	Shrivel	205	34	295
		2	Moderate	Small	196	32	234
		3	Sturdy	Small	193	30	298
		4	Sturdy	Normal	202.60	36	301
		5	Sturdy	Normal	198.50	42	298
Sweet lime (<i>Citrus limetta</i>)	Fenugreek (<i>Trigonella foenum- graecum</i>)	C	Moderate	Shrivel	182.10	27	231
		1	Moderate	Shrivel	186.80	24	246
		2	Moderate	Shrivel	138.20	27.90	256
		3	Sturdy	Normal	167.80	30	211
		4	Sturdy	Normal	188.40	44	300
		5	Sturdy	Normal	190.70	38	304

Key: FC: Fruit peel concentration, N: Nitrogen, P: Phosphorous, K: Potassium

Fig. 3 Comparison of Fenugreek Plant Appearance in Control and 5 gm Fruit Peel Treated Pots

Fig. 4 clearly illustrates the difference in growth and leaf size between the treated (T) and control (C) wheat plants after 6 days of growth. The test shows wheat plants treated with citrus fruit peel formulations had better health compared to the control group. Treated wheat plants displayed good growth in leaf size, indicating improved vigour and vitality.

Fig. 4 Comparison of Fenugreek Plant Appearance in Control and 5 gm Fruit Peel Treated Pots

Table 5 presents a comparative analysis of the effects of orange and sweet lime peels on mustard plant growth and soil nutrient content. Across both types of fruit peels, variations in plant responses are observed, particularly in stem girth and comparative leaf size. Notably, there is a noticeable trend where the concentration of fruit peel extract corresponds to an increase in soil nutrient levels, including nitrogen (N), phosphorus (P), and potassium (K). Orange peel extract tends to induce more consistent enhancements in mustard plant growth compared to sweet lime peel extract, as evidenced by improvements in stem girth and leaf size. Comparing the results across fenugreek, wheat, and mustard plants reveals varying impacts of orange and sweet lime peels on soil nutrient content and plant growth. Analysing the data, it is evident that mustard plants generally exhibit higher soil nutrient levels across nitrogen (N), phosphorus (P), and potassium (K) compared to fenugreek and wheat. Additionally, mustard plants consistently demonstrated significant improvements in stem girth and comparative leaf size when treated with both orange and sweet lime peel extracts. This suggests that mustard plants have a higher capacity to absorb and utilize nutrients from the soil, leading to better growth responses when supplemented with fruit peel extracts. On the other hand, while wheat plants also show enhancements in growth parameters with fruit peel treatments, the effects are less pronounced compared to mustard. Fenugreek plants, although responding positively to fruit peel extracts, exhibit comparatively lower increases in soil nutrient levels and growth metrics. Overall, mustard appears to benefit the most from orange and sweet lime peel treatments in terms of soil nutrient enrichment and plant growth enhancement, followed by wheat and fenugreek, respectively.

Table 5: Comparative Analysis of Orange and Sweet Lime Peels on Mustard Plant Growth and Soil Nutrient Content

Fruit peel	Plant	FC (gm/100ml D/W)	Stem Girth	Comparative Leaf Size	N (kg/ha)	P (kg/ha)	K (kg/ha)
Orange (<i>Citrus sinenses</i>)	Mustard (<i>Brassica juncea</i> L.)	Control	Sturdy	Small	198.5	23	210
		1	Moderate	Small	204	29	299
		2	Sturdy	Normal	209	36	265
		3	Moderate	Normal	204.3	38	287
		4	Moderate	Normal	210	35.9	230
		5	Moderate	Normal	210.3	39	298
Sweet lime (<i>Citrus limetta</i>)	Mustard (<i>Brassica juncea</i> L.)	FC	Stem Girth	Comparative Leaf Size	N (kg/ha)	P (kg/ha)	K (kg/ha)
		C	Moderate	Small	198.5	23	210
		1	Moderate	Small	189	25	255
		2	Sturdy	Normal	178	32	298
		3	Sturdy	Normal	199	38	302
		4	Sturdy	Normal	201	33	310
5	Sturdy	Normal	200.3	47	317		

Key: FC: Fruit peel concentration, N: Nitrogen, P: Phosphorous, K: Potassium

Fig. 5 clearly illustrates the difference in growth and leaf size between the treated (T) and control (C) mustard plants after 15 days of growth. The test results indicate a notable enhancement in the health of mustard plants treated with citrus fruit peel formulations compared to the control group. Particularly significant is the increased plant height observed in the treated mustard plants with the rise in fruit peel formulation amount.

Fig. 5 Comparison of Mustard Plant Appearance in Control and 5 gm Fruit Peel Treated Pots

IV. DISCUSSION

This study primarily focused on the utilization of paper waste, a major contributor to institutional waste. The aim was to create vermicompost using *Eisenia fetida* as study organism and Farm Yard Manure (FYM), which served as primary food for the worms. The secondary food was the waste given to the worms.

The study conducted by Manohar *et al.* demonstrated that pre-decomposed cattle dung, plant debris, and paper waste did not result in worm mortality [12]. Similarly, Garg *et al.* emphasized the necessity of pre-composting to prevent worm mortality

while studying the growth and reproduction of *E. foetida* in animal wastes [18]. Table 1 clearly illustrates that vermibiotechnology reduces waste volume and enhances the nutrient content of vermicompost, making it suitable as a biofertilizer in agriculture. Our study is consistent with the findings of Manohar *et al.* and Garg *et al.* as we implemented a 15-day pre-treatment for paper waste. Initially, 20 earthworms were introduced per setup, which increased to 67 mature worms, 55 immature worms, and 197 cocoons after 60 days. However, our study differs from that of Manohar *et al.* in terms of materials used, they utilized plant debris, paper, and FYM, whereas we employed paper, cardboard, and FYM, supplemented with dried leaves to balance the "green" material as a nitrogen source in our study. Cardboard typically has a carbon-to-nitrogen (C/N) ratio ranging from approximately 350:1 to 600:1, categorizing it as a "brown" material in composting due to its high carbon content, which likely enhanced vermicomposting. An ideal carbon-to-nitrogen (C/N) ratio for vermicomposting is approximately 50:1 or higher, cardboard served as a rich source of carbon in our study, validating a good reproduction rate.

Regarding N, P, and K, our study aligns with the findings of Manohar *et al.*, showing significant amounts of Nitrogen (0.79%), Phosphorus (2.50%), and Potassium (1.40%) after 50 days of vermicomposting in 575 grams of reduced waste to vermicompost. In our study, we observed Nitrogen at 0.96% (Compost Setup 1.2 with 2.1 kg of reduced waste), Phosphorus at 0.38% (Compost Setup 1.4 with 2.20 kg of reduced waste), and Potassium at 1.26% (Compost Setup 2.1 with 3.10 kg of reduced waste). Both studies used initial waste concentrations in different proportions, resulting in varying final macronutrient concentrations. Our study included three replicates for each setup, using 20 worms per replicate, while Manohar *et al.* conducted their study with no replications and using 50 worms. This approach enhances the statistical robustness of our findings. Additionally, our study includes heavy metal analysis results, crucial for demonstrating the commercial viability of this vermicompost. According to the fertilizer control order (FCO) standards for vermicompost to be used as fertilizer, our product exhibits negligible amounts of heavy metals, as shown in Table 2 [19]. In the study conducted by Pandey *et al.*, the bioaccumulation of heavy metals (Pb, Cd, Cu, and Cr) by three earthworm species (*Eisenia fetida*, *Lampito mauritii*, and *Perionyx excavatus*) in domestic waste vermicompost was examined. The final vermicompost was analyzed using Atomic Absorption Spectroscopy (AAS), revealing a significant reduction in metal concentrations: Pb (11.4-26.0%), Cd (48-61%), Cu (4.9-29.01%), and Cr (18.90-33.60%) at the end of the study period. Their findings are consistent with our own study where we used *Eisenia fetida*, which detected Cd (not detected), Cr (19.68%), Pb (3.42%), and Nickel (11.47%). Both studies demonstrate that vermicomposting effectively processes various types of waste, resulting in products with metal concentrations below regulatory limits [20-22]

Mercy *et al.* presented ground-breaking findings demonstrating that pomegranate, banana, orange and sweet lime peels can significantly enhance soil microbiota through micronutrient utilization [23]. Their formulated soils contained approximately twice the number of microorganisms per millilitre compared to control soils, and the application of fruit peel powder and extracts increased soil fertility, microbial activity, and subsequently, plant growth and yield. These results resonate with our own study, where we observed comparable outcomes as detailed in Tables 3, 4, and 5. In our research, we tested five different formulations ranging from 1 to 5 grams per 100 millilitres, whereas Mercy *et al.* tested three formulations: 1, 3, and 5 grams per 100, 300, and 500 millilitres of water, respectively. Our objective was to determine the optimal formulation for soil nutrition, whereas Mercy *et al.* focused on mixing various fruit peels into formulations.

Mercy *et al.* utilized a blend of pomegranate, orange, sweet lime, and banana peels, while we specifically targeted citrus peels separately [23]. Interestingly, in their study, the 1 gram per 100 millilitres formulation was most effective, whereas in ours, the 5 grams per 100 millilitres formulation showed superior results, possibly due to our use of individual citrus peels. However, our study differed from theirs in terms of nutrient content. Our most effective formulation (5 grams per 100 millilitres) demonstrated higher levels of N, P, and K compared to their formulation that showed optimal results with 1 gram per 100 millilitres, which in turn exhibited lower levels of N, P, and K compared to their 5 grams per 500 millilitres formulation, which did not yield optimal results in plant growth. Our study also aligns with Edwards *et al.* (1997), Van *et al.* (1999), and Hummel *et al.* (2016), emphasizing the importance of pre-decomposing paper waste and using cow dung as a supplementary nutrient source in vermicomposting. According to their findings, waste paper primarily consists of cellulose and hemi-cellulose (85-90%), with minimal quantities of essential elements. Earthworms cannot thrive on a diet solely composed of paper due to this nutrient deficiency. Therefore, blending paper waste with other substrates, such as cow dung, is essential to provide sufficient nutrients for earthworms. This combination is believed to contribute to the production of high-quality compost as shown in Table 1 [24-26].

Our findings also demonstrated that increasing the amount of fruit peel significantly boosted soil nutrient content, which contributed to enhanced growth across different plants, including Mustard, Wheat, and Fenugreek. For instance, the application of citrus peels at 5 grams per 100 millilitres formulation resulted in N levels of 200.3 kg/ha, P of 47 kg/ha, and K of 317 kg/ha in Mustard crops, N levels of 192.70 kg/ha, P 39 kg/ha, K 302 kg/ha for Wheat and N levels of 190.70 kg/ha, P 38 kg/ha, K 304 kg/ha for Fenugreek the N, P & K concentrations were improved for each crop compared to control. These results underscore the potential of fruit peel biofertilizers to significantly enhance soil fertility and nutrient availability, presenting a sustainable

alternative to chemical fertilizers. Our research supports the notion that fruit peel powder and extracts can effectively replace chemical fertilizers, thereby mitigating soil infertility and promoting sustainable agricultural practices.

V. CONCLUSION

In conclusion, this study has made significant strides in addressing the issue of institutional waste, particularly paper waste and fruit peel waste, by transforming them into valuable resources through the process of vermicomposting and the use of fruit peel formulations, respectively. Our experimental setups, which included controls and various combinations of FYM, paper waste, and cardboard, have demonstrated the feasibility of this approach. Notably, our study found no presence of heavy metals in the resulting compost, underscoring its safety and potential for widespread use. The progressive rate of worm reproduction observed during the study further supports the sustainability of this method. Moreover, regular maintenance of pH and moisture content over a 50-day period until the compost bins were harvested has ensured the quality of the biofertilizer produced. The promising results obtained in our study, particularly the progressive increase in Nitrogen (N), Phosphorus (P), and Potassium (K) content in fenugreek, wheat, and mustard, suggest that more efficient applications will be needed on long-term and economically important plants to bring this study to the commercial front. Therefore, we recommend further field trials using Split Plot Design (SPD) or Pooled Split Plot Design (PSPD) to validate these findings and explore their practical applications in sustainable agriculture. This study not only contributes to the body of knowledge on natural fertilizers but also opens up new avenues for waste management and sustainable agriculture.

AUTHOR CONTRIBUTION STATEMENT

The authors confirm contribution to the paper as follows: study conception and design: Snaa Mistry, R. Krishnamurthy; data collection: Snaa Mistry, Ankit Chaudhary; analysis and interpretation of results: Snaa Mistry, R. Krishnamurthy, Ankit Chaudhary; draft manuscript preparation: Snaa Mistry, Ankit Chaudhary. All authors reviewed the results and approved the final version of the manuscript.

FUNDING

No funding to declare.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

We are thankful to C. G. Bhakta Institute of Biotechnology for providing resources and Kishorbhai Institute of Agriculture Sciences and Research Centre, Uka Tarsadia University, Bardoli, Gujarat for providing research facility to conduct the trial.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors have no relevant financial or non-financial interests to disclose.

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